

NUI MAYNOOTH
Dileceall na hÉireann M^a Nuad

Commentary of Compositional Portfolio

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MU645 Portfolio Commentary

Introduction

For this commentary I will be employing certain standards of notation and terminology. The pitch notation system will be the Helmholtz pitch notation system and the software employed for analytical purposes will be Open Music, SPEAR & Sonic Visualiser. Instruments will be without capitals and work titles will be in italics and all translations are original unless otherwise written. I will be commenting on certain aspects of pieces and attempting to relate these to their goals and aims, while addressing the works' structures as wholes. Whilst also speaking about their conceptions and origins. Along with attempting to connect these works to composers or compositions with which I feel they relate to or identify with.

I – *Nine Waves* for Soprano and Clarinet in B flat.

Nine Waves was written over the Christmas term of 2011 and in early 2012 and received a performance in April 2012. This piece began out of a short text of nine sections, each of only a few lines. The goal was to compose music to each section, as independent of others and then rearrange each of the sections into a sequential formation independent of their context. The central reason for this was to create the music as a reflection of the text. With the reflections dealing both with conveyed and interpreted textual meaning, and, with the musical possibilities inherent in the text's formulation, including reading based or imagined sound material. Divorcing the immediate textual meaning from the performance was the reason for this but at the same time still having a concrete textual object there for referral in order to get a sense of the symbolic background of the work.

I numbered each section of the text (attached Fig. 1.1) and aligned it into sequences for each instrument. The sequence was as follows.

Fig. 1.1 Textual Sequence

Sop.	5	4	6	3	5.1	7	2	8	1	9
Cl.	1	9	2	8	5.1	3	7	4	6	5

So the arrangement is changed from a simple 1...9, into a more fluid disconnected text. In no part is the same text evident in both instruments apart from in the centre where the performers join. There are both macro (formal blocks) and micro-forms (text sections) in this piece and within the macro the piece features three overall sections; four up until the centre at 5.1 and five sections until the end. With the end of the piece featuring the finality of the sequence as present in its natural order and with the intended sentence (composed as the last 'wave' or textual section in the text's natural order, see below Fig. 1.2) The text is never heard in its original sequence, and even in the soprano's part the syllables are chopped and consonants are removed so as only to leave certain parts of words audible, which were decided as musical possibilities inherent in the texts formulation. The text is deliberately symbolic, and open to interpretation at the same time in order to give a sense of mystery to the piece.

Fig. 1.2 Nine Waves Text

- 1 = {Ripples,
at hand
at feet
Slip, into sleep}
- 2 = {Curve, line, break, interrupt
Dips create a texture that
lakes a current space.
Waves...high energy}
- 3 = {...like snow, clouded, distinct.
...over...
out
from the
centre}
- (text continues on next page...)

- 4 = {interact}
- 5 = {Something happened,
...under...
we are ripples of our neighbour
...without...}
- 6 = {fluidity as colour collections of
clouded drops,
it dropped.}
- 7 = {Take
Care
to
oscillate~}
- 8 = {Compress, an energy of influence.
...Streamed
through a thousand imaginings of
frozen fluidity, samples of our space...}
- 9 = {...Forced
to
be
Pooled...
Distant.}

Ben McHugh
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Nine small ideas or images with each lasting less than a minute in average form the bulk of this composition, and these were sketched with the text accompanying them. In each instrument the text was written out underneath and a graphic representation of the instruments response was written above (in the case of the soprano the text was written with graphic alterations as it were to be sung). This is shown below on the next page in the sketch material (Fig. 1.3).

These sections are shown in the score also with function brackets e.g. {1}...{9}, and appear preceding the section with which they apply to. These are often not directly aligned and often overlap.

In terms of compositional approach the piece exhibits quasi-spectral material (Spectral material is hinted at rather than used in a formal way), and properties of free atonality, with notes of tonal centers frequently occurring. Microtonal melody and harmony is as a result of melodic inflection for the most part. For this piece eight multiphonics were chosen based on their harshness and spectral qualities often accompanying the soprano and filling out a melody. Other techniques that I wanted to explore, such as breath sounds morphing into tones, where the performer varies the amount of air in the tone and filters it accordingly, vocal fry techniques and inward breathing techniques of clarinet playing are important in this piece. As such it is quite a dramatic piece, with a sense of drama and stillness both visible and latent in the piece.

Going through the work from the beginning it is possible to see the relationship between the instruments as being quite close, and indeed in order to perform this correctly one must read the full score for both parts. As the soprano relies heavily on the clarinet for cues and vice versa, the soprano also receives many of her notes from the clarinet and certain sections and harmonies are tailored in order to make performance easier.

The opening material introduces each instrument and two of the most important clarinet techniques are shown (breathing and harmonic traditional tone sounds), inflected with bends and tongue slaps. This contributes to a seemingly free-floating melodic material while being rigidly notated. Above this in the soprano part a high note followed by a low fry technique give the effect of stillness but the rise to meet the clarinet finishing at the end of the system followed by the clarinet providing an augmented variation of a melodic passage from bar 6. On the next system we see a mixture of spoken text, breath sounds, whispers and pitched techniques from both performers. This finishes section

{5} in the soprano and {1} in the clarinet moving on to {4} in the soprano at the beginning of page 2 with more spoken material, this time utilizing mouth shapes to change the timbre of the note. Multiphonics are employed in the clarinet and the same one is heard four times in different lengths. A c' between the first two gives the soprano their note, which is supported later on with the same note. And rippled or tremolo material is seen after in bar 20. This references the text 'Pooled...' and serves to support the imagery of water. A more detached section follows with note entries being extended by other instruments by means of soft attack and sustain. At the bottom of the page a second multiphonic is heard and the soprano separates the word 'interact', by means of elongation of the consonant 'r' as a rolled tongue sound and 'ah' as a long whispered vowel sound, the rest are spoken. Underneath the clarinet uses breath sounds leaps and elongated tone to air notes. Both begin a new section on the next page with the soprano beginning like on the previous page. This section is a mix of leaps flutter tonguing (which in this case is a guttural throat like technique). There is an almost unison melodic texture on bar 42 with the soprano and clarinet playing together on certain notes. In order to facilitate a better tuning of the passage and for future notes also. After this in the clarinet there is an elongated tone to air section, which contains an arpeggiated gesture centered on c#'''. The music drops in the next section and rises up with 'co-le-ti' with rapid blurred appoggiaturas in the clarinet. More sustained material follows and turns into staccato high c#''' notes accompanies by a recited text fragment. A multiphonic finishes this phrase. The rest of the piece continues in much of the same style as pages 1 and 2, and is broken by a rapid leaping gesture in bar 66 in the clarinet, this section constitutes {5.1} for both instruments and the material for both is based on text section number 5. In bar 68 we see a quick arpeggio like gesture centering on the pitch c'''. A leaping melody can be seen at the bottom of the page and at this time the clarinet is in section {3} and the soprano in {7}, this leaping moves in contrary motion and is repeated in straight rhythm in the next bar. A quasi-spectral arpeggio based on the

fundamental a appears in bar 82. In the second system of the fifth page we see more breath trill material (more of a bisbigliandi than trill in sonic effect) based on material in the beginning, above, the soprano line features predominantly spoken chopped syllabic techniques. The final page of the score returns to a more virtuosic leaping section for the clarinet, which calms down towards the end of bar 104. The final system features only one note in the soprano and the clarinet features a bend to a $1/4\#$ between a free melodic sequence finishing on air to tone in the last bar with the soprano echoing 'dis-tant', closing the text and the piece.

II – *So Calm, So...* – for Solo Voice

So Calm, So... for Solo Voice was written for the CMC Annual Student New Music Marathon in DIT Rathmines, Dublin in March 2012, in where a performance requiring the composers to source their own performers was requested. I chose to ask a colleague of mine James Garvey to perform a piece that was already in the sketching stages and we began work-shopping techniques. I already had techniques in mind from *Nine Waves* such as the fry technique, whispering and spoken syllabic text. Other techniques were added to this such as Multiphonics and inward singing (singing while breathing inwards). Vocal formant filtering was another technique employed and this is used twice in the piece for continuously altering the timbre of full chest notes. This score was handwritten in order to facilitate better notation of some of the techniques and in order to show the free rhythm nature of this work, bar lines are not used in the conventional sense and denote areas of different activity, technique or section and the rests are measured in seconds.

There are two pieces of text that constitute this work's material, the first which was the basis of the compositional material and was written with the work as a collection of

syllables of no particular meaning and the second which is a quote from one of Leonardo da Vinci's writings. The first text in its entirety is as follows (without syllabic repetition, and with full stops denoting the end of lines):

Fig. 2.1 *So Calm, So...* Text 1

Su, yah, su, ya, mi, su, ya, su. Suo, mi, kah, mm, kah, bah, tnnst, ts.

Ta, ya, mi, meh. Meh, su, maya, maye, oh, weh, su.

Ya, su, ya, mi, ko, oh, mu, o, so, le, so, mi. Ge, ki, su, ya, so, ke.

Ki, ta, pi, shh, beh.

And in the international phonetic alphabet:

su, ja, su, ja, mi, su, ja, su. Su-o, mi, ka, ɛm, ka, ba, ti ɛn strit, ties.

ta, ja, mi, me. me, su, majə, me, o, we, su.

ja, su, ja, mi, ko, o, mu, o, so, lə, so, mi. ge, ki, su, ja, so, ke.

ki, ta, paj, f, be.

This is where the piece gets its title from 'Su, kah, su' adapted to *So Calm, So*.

Vocally, this text was written to suit the types of mouth sounds that I was searching for and does not exhibit any type of conventional linguistic logic when divorced from performance.

The second piece of text was decided by its symbolic meaning with relation to what the piece could convey, well in my interpretation anyway, it also limits the abstract possibilities of the text, however there is no direct connection evident with the abstract first text and the logic based second text which speaks of seeming abstract or metaphysical pursuits. The second text follows on the next page (Fig. 2.2). It is taken from da Vinci's notes on art and life and is damning statement on his dislike for so Necromancers or practitioners who claim to be able to speak with the dead and/or raise

and control their bodies after death. Also denoting the practices of witchcraft, this term was of concern to da Vinci as he was studying anatomy and seems to vex or disturb him.

Fig. 2.1 *So Calm, So...* Text 2

I: But necromancy, the flag and flying banner, blown hither and thither by the winds, is the guide of the silly multitude, which constantly bears witness with gaping wonder to the countless effects of this art; and whole books are written which declare that incantations and spirits are efficacious and speak without tongues and without vocal organs, without which it is impossible to speak, and carry the heaviest weights, raising tempests and rain and transforming men into cats, wolves and other beasts, although they who affirm such things are the first to be transformed into beasts.

II: And certainly if such necromancy existed, as is believed by lower intellects, there is nothing on the earth which would be so effectual both as regards the service and detriment of man; because if it is true that this art has the power to disturb the calm serenity of the atmosphere, changing it into night and producing sparks and winds, with fearful thunder and lightnings that fly through the darkness, and overthrowing high buildings with violent winds and uprooting forests and striking armies and shattering and overwhelming them, and producing, in addition to this, devastating storms which rob the peasants of the fruits of their toil, what kind of warfare is there so deadly to the enemy?

III: Who in naval warfare can be compared with him who commands the winds and generates storms which ruin and sink any fleet whatsoever?¹

Leonardo da Vinci,
Thoughts on Art and Life,
(Boston: The Merrymount Press, 1906),
Trans. Maurice Baring.

Notions of late middle ages magi and witch-craft can still be seen in modern day psychic reality shows and in several shows (haunted documentaries) about the discovery of ghosts and haunted premises.

The material in this piece whether directly or indirectly attempts to reason with this, and recordings of several sections could, in fact, be used as sound effects for many twentieth century (a genre now heavily clichéd) horror films.

¹ Leonardo da Vinci, *Thoughts on Art and Life*, (Boston: The Merrymount Press, 1906), pp. 181-182.

III – VIX – for Solo Mixed Percussion

VIX, meaning 6, 10 in Roman numerals was written for a performance by the percussionist Alex Petcu as part of an ICC (Irish Composers Collective) concert in the National Concert Hall in June 2012.

A list of instruments were given and composers were asked to choose their preferences from this list as follows:

Fig. 3.1 instrument list

Instrument list

	Tuned	
Marimba		Range: A2 to C7. No harder mallets than vibe, or rubber mallets, although snare sticks can be used lightly.
	Wood	
3 mokubio wood blocks		Very high, piercing sound. Xylophone mallets or harder needed. Pitches: C#7, E(half#)7, A8
4 homemade woodblocks		Same as the ones used in the following video: http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5DYNmj9zw9g Any sticks or mallets Pitches: A(half#)6, C(half#)6, E6, G#6
5 templeblocks		Same as the ones used here: http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-nS_orfg1co Any sticks or mallets Pitches: D#5, F5, G(half#)5, C6, D6
6 blocks made from wooden pieces		Same as the ones used in: http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-nS_orfg1co Any sticks or mallets Pitches: C#5, F5, G5, C6, D6, E6
Log drum		2 different sounds Nothing harder than vibe mallets. Pitches: B3, D3
Small wooden plank		Same as the ones used in this video (listen to the start, after the shouting): http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EY5uhOZlbEo Any mallets can be used. Unpitched
Claves		Pitch: C#7
Guiro		Unpitched
Rainstick		Unpitched
	Skin	
2 sets of bongos		Any sticks or mallets
1 conga		Any sticks or mallets
3 toms		Any sticks or mallets
Snare drum		Any sticks or mallets

Metal

Cymbals	2 crash, ride, 3 splash, 3 china, broken spiral cymbal, broken trashy splash cymbal. Other cymbals may be brought, upon request. NB: I won't be able to set up more than three cymbals at once, unless somebody brings more cymbal stands. Any sticks or mallets Unpitched
3 opera gongs	2 ascending, 1 descending. They can be heard here: http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fkmdyluVo-g Any sticks or mallets Pitches: E(half#)4, G4, E5
6 cowbells	Some are quite resonant, others are not, but can be dampened anyway. Any sticks or mallets Non-resonant pitches: B(half)5, F5 Resonant pitches: A(half)5, B(half)5, B(half#)5, E5
4 brake drums	Brake drums from a car. Anvil type of sound. Any sticks or mallets Unpitched but high and nasty sound
Finger cymbals	Pitch: F#7

Other instruments

Various rattles and shakers	Unpitched
Tambourine	Unpitched
6 bottles	Approximate pitch range: A7 to E7
2 temple bowls	Pitches: G4, C#5

The instruments that were chosen from this were the homemade wood blocks, the log drum, the cymbals, opera gongs, break drums, the temple bowls, two toms, wooden planks (6 blocks made from wooden pieces) and the cowbells. And the sticks employed were drumsticks, hot-rods, brushes, xylophone, rubber, marimba and timpani mallets, hands (as mallets) and bow. These led to various possible combinations of timbre with stick and instrument combinations and four possible sounds to be played simultaneously, giving the composition much timbral freedom. Extremes of dynamic and spectral thickness were employed and elements of extreme loud dynamic (bar 109) and then quiet following to provide an aural illusion.

The score was then laid out with two staves (see Fig. 3.2) one for the left hand side of the performance area and one for the right mimicking the piano's grand staff layout. With the performer standing in the centre of the instruments, before the toms. Then a

special notation system was designed with note heads and spaces denoting which instrument was to be played and this is shown on the first page of the score.

Fig. 3.2 Arrangement of percussion instruments

I then researched many works for solo percussionist from composers that appealed to me, and I came across a piece by Helmut Lachenmann titled *Interieur I* (1965-66) from his *Interieur* series of works. *Interieur I*, which had wide ranging shifts of timbre and rhythm, this influenced this work to a large extent along with Xenakis's *Persephassa* (1970). Another piece that influenced this was Billone's *Mani. De Leonardis* (2004) for four Automobile Springs and Glass, which appealed to me due to its loose sense of time and preference for sharp inharmonic timbres. After researching these pieces and studying some of their scores the piece went into the sketching stages.

Fig. 3.3 Sketch of VIX

The image shows a handwritten musical score sketch for a piece titled 'VIX'. The score is written on six staves, each with various musical notations and performance instructions. The top staff is labeled 'Intro' and contains notes with '100' written above them. The second staff is labeled 'Song 1' and features a 'MODAL' section. The third staff is labeled 'Outside' and includes 'Cymbals' and 'Drum' markings. The fourth staff is labeled 'Free' and contains 'Heavy' and 'P.P.' markings. The fifth staff is labeled 'Song 2' and includes 'do just (ala loch)' and 'Sons, move out' markings. The sixth staff is labeled 'Out' and contains 'Drum' and 'draw' markings. The bottom of the page has a large handwritten expression: $\{ (6, 10), (60, 100), (0.6, 1) \}$.

The sketching process was quite fluid, and the piece was written out into six panels numbered 1 to 6, each taking a line of the sketch notation paper. These were given titles or moods and were decided on being about 1'20" each and each lasting a page on notation paper. These are 1: Intro (based on C), 2: Song 1 (based on E \flat), 3: Outside (based on G), 4: Free (based on E), 5: Song 2 (based on G) and 6: Out (based on B). These pitches were taken from the pitched list of percussion and extrapolated from harmonic series to give an impression of the fundamental in question. With special attention to common upper partials and microtonal overtones.

The score was edited and many bars were taken away to facilitate a shorter work with the intended length to be 150 – 160 bars being restricted to 114 and the final page of

section 6 discarded. VIX also can be written as the Latin word Vix which means barely, or scarcely.

IV – *Zdaleka* – for Flute and Piano (2011/2012)

Zdaleka, written for Flute and Piano is the shortest work of the portfolio. Sketched and Drafted in late 2011 it is the oldest along with *Nine Waves*: written at the end of 2011.

This work entitled *Zdaleka* from Czech language meaning from far away or from afar, attempts to reason the difference between two different types of music: temporal rhythm and time based music with sound that seems to exist outside of time in an imagined a-temporal space. As such the work can be broken up into various sections decided in the sketching stages of this work. Half of the work's material was written in 2011 and half written a year later in 2012. Before attempting to connect the two different styles, a certain musical journey, or timeline of influence must be addressed. The first part written which is actually the second part of the work exists in the a-temporal space. And this begins on page 2 starting at bar 18. It features leap arpeggio like crystalline piano gestures that last for five quaver beats. These have two levels: the left hand and the right hand. The notes of this first sequence are e'', b b'', f'', c#''', & f'''. The left hand taking the e'' & b b''. This gesture is repeated three times with each time beginning on a different beat within a 4/4 bar. The first being on 1st quaver beat of 8, the second on the 6th of 8 and the third beginning on the 2nd of 8 in the subsequent bar. There being a 13 quaver beat difference between the instance of the first and second and a 12 quaver beat difference between the second and third instances. Following this, the pattern contracts by one quaver each time so that in subsequent instances the pattern is shorter and denser and notes fall upon each other in harmony, this is caused by the left hand being moved forward and the right hand remaining stationary. And this contributes to a sharp celestial like feel akin to works by many composers such as Morton Feldman and Arvo Pärt.

These would be the first area of influence in this work along with Kaija Saariaho who influenced the piece indirectly in terms of the subject matter of her recent opera *L'Amour de loin* (2000). 'L'Amour de loin', from French which translates to 'a love from afar' or to 'the love from afar'. Played a central role in the naming and conception of the piece. Influencing ideas of echoed gestures, disconnects between instruments and of sounds transformed by distance. Through the 2nd section of five note piano arpeggios the flute is more disconnected from the instruments than as heard previously providing more of a background sonority, it temporally re-appears in bar 23 with a tongue slap to air and up to D''''.

The material, which is more temporal or pointillistic, features at the start of the work. This was written before the following material, and it is split into two sections. After the opening silent 3/4 bar introduction there is a low appoggiatura in the left hand which jumps to a high e b'''''. This note can be considered as the key-tone of the piece or the note with which the most material is drawn to. The low staccato interval and sustained note following contributes to a sense of disorientation and discontinuity, this is extended with shorter time between the low and the high attack. This is reminiscent of the upper frequency spectrum of the piano's timbre. The e b''''' being and upper partial of the lower a b,,. This receives harmonic interference from its neighbour note of g, a minor second below which filters up to the e b'''''. In bar 4 the second sustained note is replaced by a harmonic, elicited by placing the finger of the right hand on a node of the piano string, the intended resulting pitch to be c' or middle C. This harmonic can be found by fingering a node at 1/6 the length of the piano string the closest to the keyboard being just after the horizontal frame, this harmonic is $f/5$ of A b, or the 4th overtone. The leap in the flute is intended to echo the first high notes in the piano and it introduces an f#''', in order to bridge the gap between low and high. f#''' can also be rationalized as g b''

which is close to (g 3/4 b) being *f/7* of A \flat , , and fitting into the harmonic series of A \flat , . This is further varied with the introduction of longer notes in both the piano and flute interspersed with low accented grounding gestures the lower two note cluster changes to G \sharp , & A, and this drops a tone. There is then a harmonic ‘filling out’ of the higher d’’ and the lower F, in the piano and the flute supports the f’’ for a short time, blending both instruments. This high note then changes to an air note introducing more inharmonicity into the flute’s timbre. The Piano’s bass supports the entry. Throughout the following bars these gestures are introduced at different times and broken up with new notes introduced, the flute stays as a more sustained force with the piano contributing to a more pontillistic percussive texture while at the same time supporting the flute with harmony from time to time. This part finishes at the end of the second system on the first page.

In the second part of the first section, the piano takes more of a sustaining role with the flute more staccato and rhythmic. The piano extends the flute’s notes with held harmonic notes and also mimics percussive material seen earlier, it also introduces or echoes certain notes that the flute is about to play or has played contributing to a stronger relationship between the two. And this section finishes with a piano ‘leading note’ d’’ to the next ‘a-temporal’ section’s (discussed earlier) first note of e’’.

V – Матрёшки – (*Matrioshki*) for Bass Clarinet and Violoncello

Матрёшки, hereafter referred to as *Matrioshki* meaning nested dolls, or more commonly known as Russian dolls, is the final piece in this portfolio and indeed the longest. It is slightly longer than *Nine Waves* and is the only piece to feature a string instrument. It employs several of the clarinet techniques seen earlier in *Nine Waves* and some new techniques such as harmonics beating or difference tones, multiphonic shifting and finger adjustment to create inter-timbral changes. The cello features *col legno battuto*, multiphonics (elicited by applying increased bow pressure on a harmonic node) and Bartók slap pizzicato.

The title refers to the ideas of recursion and self-similarity, with the Russian dolls serving as a physical representation of this. Another example is that of a snow globe with a smaller snow globe inside and a smaller one inside that. The idea that inside an object, image (parallel mirrors or video feedback) or sound (complex tones and spectra), there may be an infinite number of smaller parts that mirror a larger whole. Thus this piece relies on the principal of spectral harmony and harmony that mimics multiphonics (e.g. the harmonic relationship between the Bass Clarinet and Cello in bars 13 and 14) and arpeggios are used to mimic spectra.

This piece was written based on a cantus firmus that I devised over a leaping bass figuration. This features a sequence that could potentially repeat ad-infinitum. The sequence of five notes and five intervals, which can start in any octave begins on the note E and drops 1 semitone to E \flat , rises a major third to G and drops a minor sixth to B and then rises a perfect fourth to back to E, this then drops a perfect fifth to A \flat . This cycle then repeats. It is harmonized below in the bass as follows C, A \flat , E and this is repeated. This is shown in the music below (Fig. 5.2).

Fig. 5.2 Cantus Firmus

Although the piece is based on this sequence it is never directly apparent and it forms more of a background to the work. However it is the bass harmony that is directly used in a formal way and the piece relies heavily on this. The ideal spectra ($f 1/1 \dots f 1/16$) of the notes C, A \flat , and E \flat were found and the form of the work was arranged into six sections (A, B, C, D, E & F) and these were divided into two parts of three (An exposition and a development). Each of the instruments was given a spectrum to play within for each section, the sequence was as follows.

Fig. 5.3 Spectral Forms

Section	A	B	C	D	E	F
B. Cl.	A \flat	E	C	A \flat	E	C
Vc.	C	A \flat	E	C	A \flat	E

This was the guideline for the pitched and multiphonic material for each instrument (however it was not so strict and there is deviation outside of these spectra.)

For each spectra there was a multiphonic chosen and other multiphonics as external influence were employed also.

Below is the sketch of *Matrioshki* and the form can be seen clearly along with a visual representation of the music within the score, with black pen (upper) representing the bass clarinet and the red (lower) representing the cello.

Fig. 5.4 Sketch of *Matrioshki*

The image shows a handwritten musical score on a piece of paper. The score is written in black ink for the upper part (bass clarinet) and red ink for the lower part (cello). The notation includes various musical symbols such as notes, rests, and dynamic markings. There are also some performance instructions and annotations in red ink. At the bottom right of the page, the title '2012 МАТРЕШКИ' is written in red ink.

Along with the spectra, the piece features a text of four words (in Russian) written in both Latin and Cyrillic script, these are as follows (on the next page):

Russian (Cyrillic Script)	–	Russian (Latin)	–	English Translation
В	–	V	–	In
ВНУТРИ	–	Vnutri	–	Within
ВНУТРЕННИЙ	–	Vnutrenniy	–	Inner, Interior
ВНЕШНИЙ	–	Vneshniy	–	External

These words are spoken by both performers, at separate places throughout the work and allude to the idea of the Russian doll, particularly to inner ones where they are simultaneously inside something and outside another. The same way for example we are inside the park but outside a building. These linguistic signifiers are very important in this work, and the journey into the interior of an object to come out the other side forms a large part of the conceptual framework of the piece.

Bibliography

da Vinci, Leonardo, *Thoughts on Art and Life*,
(Boston: The Merrymount Press, 1906), Trans. Maurice Baring.

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